

Ferroelastic phase transition in lead bismuth borate, PbBiOBO_3

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Abstract

For lead bismuth borate, PbBiOBO_3 , two different room-temperature crystal structures are reported in literature. Addressing this discrepancy, in the present work by means of temperature-dependent polarisation microscopy, dilatometry, calorimetry, Raman spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction crystals of PbBiOBO_3 are studied and a structural phase transition is discovered and characterised. The crystal structures of both, the high- and the low-temperature phase are determined, with space group symmetry $Cmce$ (Nr. 64) and $P112_1/a$ (Nr. 14), respectively. The second order phase transition at 315 K is of displacive, proper ferroelastic type (Aizu species $mmmF2/m$). The components of the tensor of thermal expansion of the high-temperature phase are constant with temperature, while in the low-temperature phase a linear temperature dependence of the thermal expansion coefficients is found. From X-ray powder diffraction data, the spontaneous strain components are calculated. The symmetry-breaking spontaneous strain ε_{12} shows quadratic temperature dependence, underlining the second order character of the phase transition.

Keywords: lead bismuth borate; ferroelastic phase transition; thermal expansion; spontaneous strain; Raman spectroscopy

1. Introduction

The influence of lone electron pairs in crystal structures on the magnitude of physical properties that benefit from pronounced structural polarity, such as second harmonic generation, pyro- or piezoelectricity, is considered since many years, see, e.g., review articles [1-3] and references therein. In recent years, also a variety of new crystals with two types of lone-pair cations have been synthesized, for example Pb_3SeO_5 [4], PbFIO_3 [5], or $\text{BiO}(\text{IO}_3)$ [6] and it turned out, that these compounds indeed show large second harmonic generation response. This suggests that the combination of multiple lone-pair cations in a crystal structure may enhance the potential of the above-mentioned type of materials. Already forty years ago, investigations in the system $\text{PbO-Bi}_2\text{O}_3\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3$, where the two lone-pair cations Pb^{2+} and Bi^{3+} are present, had been performed by J. Liebertz, mastering the particular challenge of crystal growth from glass-forming melts of high viscosity [7]. In this context, besides the nowadays well-known nonlinear optical crystal BiB_3O_6 also PbBiOBO_3 had been grown to large single crystals. However, PbBiOBO_3 turned out to be centrosymmetric and therefore was not further pursued (and not published) at that time.

More than twenty years later the crystal structure of PbBiOBO_3 , synthesized by solid state reaction, was reported with monoclinic symmetry (space group $P2_1/n$, Nr. 14) [8, 9], but a few years after also as an orthorhombic ($Cmca$) structure [10], with both structures based on room temperature X-ray diffraction data. For the latter orthorhombic phase theoretical refractive indices were calculated using the DFT method [11].

Given the fact of the discrepancy between the two different reported structural data, in the present study we investigated the temperature-dependent properties of PbBiOBO_3 by means of heating stage polarization microscopy, single-crystal and powder X-ray diffraction, thermal expansion (dilatometry), Raman spectroscopy and calorimetry using the single crystals grown by our late colleague J. Liebertz.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Crystal growth

The compound PbBiOBO_3 shows congruent melting behaviour with a melting point at 916 K, as determined by differential thermal analysis (DTA). Therefore, in general, single crystals of PbBiOBO_3 can be grown from a melt of the same composition as that of the crystal. However, a slight excess of ~ 3 mol% PbO is useful because it lessens the viscosity of the melt. The crystals were grown by the top-seeding technique using a platinum crucible of 100 ml volume and a resistance furnace. In [Fig. 1](#) an example of a grown single crystal of PbBiOBO_3 is presented. The grown crystals show many cracks but contain large undisturbed regions and well-developed morphological faces, which were used as basis for the preparation of crystallographically oriented samples. For the indexing of the morphological faces the lattice parameters of the orthorhombic crystal structure of PbBiOBO_3 given in [\[10\]](#) was used.

Figure 1: Example of a single crystal of PbBiOBO_3 grown by the top-seeding technique by J. Liebertz. The crystal shows a rough growth surface and some flat morphological faces, and contains large clear, undisturbed regions.

2.2 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC measurements were performed with a coarsely powdered sample using a Perkin Elmer DSC 7 calorimeter with LN_2 cooling and dry N_2 purge gas. Caloric calibration was performed with an indium calibration standard. Three consecutive heating/cooling cycles with a heating/cooling rate of $20^\circ/\text{min}$ were applied.

2.3 Temperature-dependent polarization microscopy

Using a Linkam THMS600 heating stage with LN_2 cooling and dry N_2 purge gas, mounted on an Olympus BH-2 polarization microscope, temperature-dependent polarization microscopy investigations were performed. The observations were made with three polished plate-shaped samples of ca. 0.1 mm thickness, each, with plate faces (100), (010) and (001), respectively (referring, as above, to the reference system of the orthorhombic crystal structure). Microscopy images in the temperature range from 232 K to 343 K were taken with a digital tablet camera VisiCam TC10 adapted on the microscope tube. Several heating/cooling cycles with rates of 10 K/min. were applied and interrupted several times by short dwells to capture images.

2.4 Dilatometric measurements

For the determination of thermal expansion by means of temperature-dependent dilatometry a parallel-epipedal sample of PbBiOBO_3 with faces (100), (010) and (001) (related to orthorhombic axes, as above) with dimensions 5.67 x 4.57 x 3.19 mm was used. Dilatometric measurement of the

temperature-dependence of the respective sample length L along the orthorhombic a^{or} -, b^{or} - and c^{or} -axis was performed with a thermomechanical analyser Perkin Elmer TMA 7 (with inductive registration of the sample length L) in flowing dry N_2 atmosphere. For each of the three crystallographic directions $[100]^{\text{or}}$, $[010]^{\text{or}}$ and $[001]^{\text{or}}$ three subsequent heating/cooling cycles with a heating rate of $\pm 1^\circ/\text{min}$. were applied within the temperature range from 228 K to 413 K, starting for each direction the initial measurement at the lowest temperature of 228 K. Between the measurement sequences for the different directions the crystal sample always was stored at room temperature over 2-3 days.

2.5 Temperature-dependent powder X-ray diffraction

Temperature-dependent X-ray powder diffraction measurements were performed using the Debye-Scherrer transmission configuration on a PANalytical Empyrean powder diffractometer ($\text{CuK}\alpha$, $\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) equipped with a focusing mirror, a capillary holder, a PIXcel3D detector, and an Oxford Cryostream 700 plus cooler. The measurements were performed at constant temperature steps, ranging from $2\theta = 4^\circ$ to $2\theta = 90^\circ$, with a 0.013° stepwidth, and each measurement lasted 60 minutes. The temperature was changed by the rate of 6 K min^{-1} between individual scans in temperature steps of 5 K between 210 K and 400 K. Because of the high X-ray absorption of PbBiOBO_3 the powder sample was diluted with diamond powder of $6 \mu\text{m}$ grain size (diamond: $\text{PbBiOBO}_3 \approx 82:18 \text{ wt\%}$), which also served as an internal standard for the measurements. The sample was ground, placed into a borosilicate capillary with a diameter of 0.3 mm and sealed with rubber.

2.6 Crystal structure determination

Crystallographic data for both phases of PbBiOBO_3 were obtained on a Bruker diffractometer D8 VENTURE Kappa Duo PHOTONIII by μS micro-focus sealed tube $\text{MoK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The crystal temperature during data acquisition was preserved by the Cryostream Cooler 1000. The structures were solved by direct methods (XT) [12] and refined by full matrix least squares based on F^2 (SHELXL2019) [13].

The measurement started at a temperature of 290 K, corresponding to the low-temperature phase. Monoclinic space group $P112_1/a$ was selected based on the symmetry of the high-temperature phase $Cmca$. The positions of Pb and Bi atoms were ascribed in accordance with expected values of bond valence 2 and 3 for Pb and Bi, respectively. The very high absorption coefficient affects the data reduction and, consequently, the displacement parameters of atoms, which were therefore constrained during refinement to preserve their physical meaning. Immediately after the measurement at 290 K was completed, the crystal was heated to 340 K to pass the phase transition and was measured again. X-ray crystallographic data have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre under deposition numbers CCDC 2499671 and 2499672 for the monoclinic low-temperature and the orthorhombic high-temperature phases of PbBiOBO_3 , respectively. They can be obtained free of charge from the Centre via its website (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures/>). The crystallographic data, data collection, and refinement parameters are summarised in Table S1 in the Supplementary Materials.

2.7 Vibrational spectroscopy

The FTIR spectra of powdered samples were recorded on a Thermo Fisher Scientific Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer (4 cm^{-1} resolution, Happ-Genzel apodization) in the $400 - 4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (KBr beamsplitter) and $50 - 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Solid Substrate™ beamsplitter) regions using the Nujol mull technique. The spectra were also recorded using the ATR technique (diamond crystal) in the $400 - 4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (KBr beamsplitter) and $100 - 1800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Solid Substrate™ beamsplitter). Standard ATR correction implemented in Omnic software [14] was applied to the recorded spectra.

The temperature-dependent Raman spectra of the powdered sample were recorded in backscattering geometry on a Thermo Scientific DXR Raman Microscope interfaced to an Olympus microscope (objective 10x) in the $25 - 1800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral region (830 lines/mm grating, $\sim 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ resolution) using unpolarised frequency-stabilised 780 nm single-mode diode laser excitation (20 mW power). The spectrometer was calibrated using a software-controlled calibration procedure that employed multiple

neon emission lines (wavelength calibration), multiple polystyrene Raman bands (laser frequency calibration), and standardised white light sources (intensity calibration). The sample was placed in the Linkam Scientific Instruments FTIRSP600 temperature-controlled stage, controlled by LinSys32 software in the temperature range of 95-400 K. The spectra were recorded at 10 K steps during cooling (from 395 K to 215 K) and heating (from 210 K to 400 K) runs. The cooling/heating rate between steps was 5 K/min. The maxima of the recorded bands were obtained by the fitting process implemented in the Omnic software [14] (Voigt profile; high sensitivity; linear baseline and noise target 10.0). Additionally, the Raman spectra were also collected at temperatures of 175 K, 135 K, and 95 K.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Temperature-dependent polarisation microscopy

While observation at 298 K of the (100) and the (010) sample between crossed polarisers reveals no conspicuous features but homogeneous, parallel extinction with respect to the orthorhombic axes, the polarisation microscopy image of the (001) sample (again at 298 K in crossed polarised light) shows lamellae of twin domains of two differently oriented twin states (“orientation states”, OS) with mutually orthogonal domain walls that run parallel to the orthorhombic a^{or} - and the b^{or} -axis, as can be seen in Fig. 2a. The two different orientation states can clearly be distinguished by their extinctions in cross-polarised light, which make an extinction angle with the domain walls of $+8^\circ$ (OS 1) and -8° (OS 2), see Fig. 2b. Here, monochromatic light (with wavelength $\lambda = 546.7$ nm) is used to enhance the visual contrast between lamellae in extinction and out-of-extinction lamellae. With a sketch (Fig. 2c) the mutual orientation of domain walls and respective elliptic sections of the optical indicatrix of the two types of orientation states is illustrated schematically.

Figure 2: (a) (001) plate of PbBiOBO_3 in cross-polarised white light, showing mutually orthogonal, horizontal and vertical domain walls of domains of two different orientation states. (b) (001) plate of PbBiOBO_3 in cross-polarised, monochromatic light ($\lambda = 546.7$ nm). Left image: sample rotated by $+8^\circ$ out of the vertical orientation of the domain walls into extinction of orientation state 1 (OS1), indicated by dark lamellae of this orientation state; Right image: sample rotated by -8° out of the vertical orientation of the domain walls into extinction of orientation state 2 (OS2), indicated by dark colour of the complementary lamellae. The crossed arrows mark the polarisation directions of the two polarisation filters (p: polariser; a: analyser) of the microscope. (c) Schematic sketch of the orientation of the respective elliptic section of the optical indicatrix in the lamellae of OS1 and OS2. The principal axes of the elliptic sections are tilted by $+8^\circ$ for OS2 and -8° for OS1 out of the direction of the domain walls. Note that the degree of ellipticity of the elliptic sections is enhanced for better visibility and does not represent the actual birefringence of the domains of PbBiOBO_3 .

Applying a temperature change to the crystal during polarisation microscopy observation reveals no change of their optical behaviour for the (100) and (010) samples within the entire applied temperature range from 232 K to 343 K. For the (001) sample, however, the domain structure visible at 298 K fades out at ~ 326 K (see Fig. 3), leaving the crystal sample without any twinning above 326 K, with homogeneous, full extinction parallel to the directions of the former domain walls, i.e. the directions of the orthorhombic a^{or} - and b^{or} -axes. On cooling, the twin lamellae emerge again sharply below 326 K, however, with a subtly changed domain structure with a weak dominance of one of the two domain wall orientations (horizontal domain walls in the case shown in Fig. 3). This domain

structure remains stable down to the lowest applied temperature of 232 K. The heating/cooling cycles can be repeated several times without damage of the crystal and with the same result. After having stored the crystal sample for approx. 24 hours at 298 K the (approximate) initial domain structure has recovered.

Figure 3: Temperature-dependent polarisation microscopy images of PbBiOBO_3 recorded at the indicated temperatures. All images are taken with cross-polarised light. The crystal sample is rotated by $\sim 4^\circ$ out of horizontal/vertical orientation of the domain walls (i.e. the orthorhombic a^{or} - and b^{or} -axes) for sufficient contrast between the twin lamellae. Fading of the interference colours and disappearance of the domain structure of the crystal for temperatures above ~ 326 K indicates the emergence of an orthorhombic phase in the course of a phase transformation, with the crystal sample being rotated slightly out of the extinction position.

This temperature-dependent optical behaviour of PbBiOBO_3 , illustrated in Fig. 3, is an indication of the occurrence of a phase transition of ferroelastic type, where the phase transformation is characterised by the emergence of tensor components unequal zero of the spontaneous strain tensor of the crystal. Considering the orientation of the optical indicatrix above and below the phase transition, where extinction parallel to all orthorhombic axes is given at temperatures above 326 K, while inclined extinction with respect to the orthorhombic a^{or} - and b^{or} -axes and parallel extinction with the c^{or} -axis is observed at temperatures below 326 K, the ferroelastic phase transition goes in hand with a symmetry change from orthorhombic to monoclinic symmetry (with decreasing temperature). During the symmetry change the orthorhombic c^{or} -axis of the high-temperature phase turns into the monoclinic axis of the low-temperature modification of the crystal.

The evidence of a ferroelastic, structural phase transition in crystals of PbBiOBO_3 motivates a re-determination of crystal structure at temperatures above and below the phase transition temperature as well as a more detailed investigation of the phase transition itself.

3.2 Structural investigations

At 340 K crystals of PbBiOBO_3 possess orthorhombic symmetry with space group $Cmce$ (Nr.64), lattice constants are listed in Table 1, atomic positions and thermal displacement parameters are listed in Table S2 in the Supplementary Materials. In the structure both, bismuth and lead are irregularly 6-fold coordinated by oxygen, with three shorter (2.299 Å – 2.307 Å) and three longer (2.790 Å – 2.909 Å) Pb-O bonds and Bi-O bond lengths of 2.186 Å, 2.377 Å and 2.551 Å (for two Bi-O bonds, each). The lone electron pairs present for both, Pb^{2+} and Bi^{3+} , make strong impact on the resulting coordination polyhedra $[\text{PbO}_6]$ and $[\text{BiO}_6]$, where the cations are positioned pronouncedly off-center in the strongly distorted coordination polyhedra, as can be seen in Fig. 4a. $[\text{BiO}_6]$ polyhedra set up $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ dimers by sharing common edges, i.e., two common oxygen ligands (Fig. 4b). The $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ dimers are corner-linked to sheets running parallel (010), which alternate with sheets of corner connected $[\text{PbO}_6]$

polyhedra and $[\text{BO}_3]$ groups to form a three-dimensions structural network. A view along the a -axis of the crystal structure is given in Fig. 5.

Figure 4: Structural details of the crystal structure of the orthorhombic high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 showing coordination polyhedral $[\text{BiO}_6]$ (green), $[\text{PbO}_6]$ (orange) and $[\text{BO}_3]$ (violet). Oxygen ligands are plotted as blue spheres, the unit cell and the respective directions of the crystallographic axes of the structure are indicated. (a) View approximately along direction $[1\bar{1}0]$, illustrating the connections between coordination polyhedral in the structural network. The impact of the stereochemically active lone electron pairs of Pb^{2+} and Bi^{3+} are visible by the pronounced off-center position of Pb, resp. Bi, in its respective coordination surrounding. (b) Sheet of corner-linked dimer groups $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ that are composed of two edge-sharing $[\text{BiO}_6]$ coordination polyhedral, each. The sheets of interlinked $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_{10}]$ dimers run parallel (010) .

Figure 5: View of the crystal structure of orthorhombic PbBiOBO_3 along the c -axis. $[\text{BiO}_6]$ coordination polyhedra are given in green, $[\text{PbO}_6]$ coordination polyhedra in orange. Boron atoms are marked by violet, oxygen atoms by blue spheres. The unit cell and the directions of the crystallographic axes are indicated. In this view the composition of the structural network, made up of sheets of interlinked Bi-coordination polyhedra, alternating with sheets of linked $[\text{PbO}_6]$ and $[\text{BO}_3]$ groups is clearly visible.

The monoclinic crystal structure of the low-temperature modification of PbBiOBO_3 arises out of the orthorhombic high-temperature modification by only tiny displacements of atoms and the overall structural architecture is very close to that of the orthorhombic phase. At 290 K, below the above reported ferroelastic phase transition, the crystals possess space group symmetry $P11\frac{2_1}{a}$ (Nr. 14), here, a non-standard setting with monoclinic axis c was chosen since the orthorhombic c -axis turns into the monoclinic axis of the low-temperature modification of the crystal during the phase transition,

as pointed out in chapter 3.1. Lattice constants are listed in [Table 1](#), atomic positions and thermal displacement parameters are listed in [Table S2](#) in the Supplementary Materials.

Table 1: Lattice parameters of the orthorhombic and the monoclinic phase of PbBiOBO_3 .

	orthorhombic	monoclinic
temperature [K]	340	290
space group	$C \frac{2}{m} \frac{2}{c} \frac{2_1}{e}$	$P11 \frac{2_1}{a}$
$a^{\text{or}} / a^{\text{m}}$ [Å]	10.7801(6)	10.5006(3)
$b^{\text{or}} / b^{\text{m}}$ [Å]	10.5113(6)	7.5946(2)
$c^{\text{or}} / c^{\text{m}}$ [Å]	7.5240(4)	7.5282(2)
γ [°]		134.8127(5)

Our crystal structures of the high- and of the low-temperature modification of PbBiOBO_3 are in good agreement with the structure data of orthorhombic [10] and monoclinic [8, 9] PbBiBO_4 reported in literature.

In the Supplementary Materials also a comparison of selected bond lengths and bonding angles of the two modifications of PbBiOBO_3 is given in [Fig. S1](#), which illustrates the only tiny displacive structural changes that arise during the structural phase transition. In both crystal structures the atomic displacement parameters of all atoms are rather small with no anomalies and no hint to disorder of the structures is found.

The knowledge of the polymorphy of PbBiOBO_3 and the symmetry of its high- and low-temperature phase corroborates the above finding from temperature-dependent polarisation microscopy of the occurrence of a ferroelastic structural phase transition. The phase transformation can be classified as of displacive type and of Aizu species $mmmF2/m$ [15]. The parent (prototypic) phase with point group $\frac{2}{m} \frac{2}{m} \frac{2}{m}$ with group order 8 transforms into the ferroelastic phase of point group $\frac{2}{m}$ with group order 4, accompanied by the loss of four symmetry elements, $\{2_a, 2_b, m_a, m_b\}$. The number of possible orientation states of the low-temperature phase is given by the ratio of the group orders and equals 2, the two orientation states are interrelated by the lost symmetry elements. According to the analysis of domain wall orientations by Sapriel [16] the permissible domain wall orientations in the case of Aizu species $mmmF2/m$ are parallel to the lost mirror planes m_a and m_b . This is in perfect agreement with the results of the heating stage polarisation microscopy observations in PbBiOBO_3 reported in chapter 3.1.

The knowledge of the space group symmetry of the high- and the low-temperature phase, respectively (i.e., $C \frac{2}{m} \frac{2}{c} \frac{2_1}{e}$ (Nr. 64) and $P11 \frac{2_1}{a}$ (Nr. 14)), allows further to classify the phase transition as of proper ferroelastic type, corresponding to the irreducible representation Γ_2^+ of space group Nr. 64 [17].

To enable a comparison of the properties of the high-temperature and the low-temperature modification of PbBiOBO_3 in the following, the monoclinic unit cell of the low-temperature phase with lattice constants $a^{\text{m}}, b^{\text{m}}, c^{\text{m}}, \gamma$ is transformed to a unit cell that is more similar to the unit cell of the orthorhombic high-temperature phase. This new monoclinic reference system (labelled in the following with capital letters $A^{\text{m}}, B^{\text{m}}, C^{\text{m}}, \Gamma$) results via $\vec{A}^{\text{m}} = -\vec{a}^{\text{m}} - 2\vec{b}^{\text{m}}, \vec{B}^{\text{m}} = \vec{a}^{\text{m}}, \vec{C}^{\text{m}} = \vec{c}^{\text{m}}$, the monoclinic angle Γ results from the scalar product $(\vec{A}^{\text{m}} \cdot \vec{B}^{\text{m}})$. The unit cell volume is twice the volume of the primitive, "old" unit cell with lattice constants $a^{\text{m}}, b^{\text{m}}, c^{\text{m}}, \gamma$. For the lattice constant data of the monoclinic phase at 290 K given above in [Table 1](#) the transformed lattice constants are $A^{\text{m}} = 10.7774$ (3) Å, $B^{\text{m}} = 10.5006$ (3) Å, $C^{\text{m}} = 7.5282$ (2) Å, $\Gamma = 89.507$ (1)°. The sketch in [Fig. 6](#) illustrates the relation between the orthorhombic reference system $\{\vec{a}^{\text{or}}, \vec{b}^{\text{or}}, \vec{c}^{\text{or}}\}$, the monoclinic reference system of the

crystal structure refinement given above, $\{\vec{a}^m, \vec{b}^m, \vec{c}^m, \gamma\}$, and the new transformed monoclinic reference system $\{\vec{A}^m, \vec{B}^m, \vec{C}^m, \Gamma\}$.

Further, for the handling of tensorial properties a cartesian reference system $\{\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3\}$ is introduced, with $\vec{e}_1 = \frac{1}{a^{or}} \vec{a}^{or}$, $\vec{e}_2 = \frac{1}{b^{or}} \vec{b}^{or}$ and $\vec{e}_3 = \frac{1}{c^{or}} \vec{c}^{or}$, which is equally applicable for the monoclinic phase of PbBiOBO_3 , since here $\vec{c}^{or} \parallel \vec{C}^m \parallel \vec{e}_3$, $\vec{b}^{or} \parallel \vec{B}^m \parallel \vec{e}_2$ and $\vec{e}_1 = (\vec{e}_2 \times \vec{e}_3) \parallel \vec{a}^{or}$.

Figure 6: Sketch of the relation between the used reference systems and unit cells. Red arrows, labelled $\vec{a}^{or}, \vec{b}^{or}, \vec{c}^{or}$, mark the axes of the reference system and the edges of the unit cell (shaded in red) of the orthorhombic high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 with space group $C_{2v}^{21} \frac{21}{m} \frac{21}{c} \frac{21}{e}$ (Nr. 64). With green colour the crystallographic axes $\vec{a}^m, \vec{b}^m, \vec{c}^m$ and monoclinic angle γ and the unit cell of the monoclinic low-temperature phase with space group $P11 \frac{21}{a}$ (Nr. 14, unique axis c , cell choice 1), as refined from the single-crystal diffraction data (see above), are indicated. The transformed monoclinic reference system $\{\vec{A}^m, \vec{B}^m, \vec{C}^m, \Gamma\}$, as described in the text, and the respective unit cell are indicated with blue colour.

3.3 Thermal analysis and thermal expansion

Thermal analysis by differential scanning calorimetry of the phase transition in PbBiOBO_3 , performed with three heating/cooling cycles, shows only a slight change in specific heat Δc_p , which expresses itself by a weak sigmoidal curvature of the DSC measurement, see Fig. 7. No indication of a phase transition enthalpy ΔH , i.e. a peak of the DSC curve, is found, which allows a classification of the phase transition as purely second order. From the DSC heating measurement data the specific heat change was determined as $\Delta c_p = 2.1(4) \text{ J/mol}\cdot\text{K}$.

Figure 7: Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements of PbBiOBO_3 in the temperature range of its phase transition, showing three heating/cooling runs with heating/cooling rate of 20 K/min. The slight s-shaped curvature of the measurement curves, that indicates a small change of specific heat Δc_p is highlighted, the small double-headed arrow marks Δc_p of one of the heating runs.

Dilatometric measurements for determination of thermal expansion in the temperature range from 228 K to 413, measured with three subsequent heating/cooling cycles on a single crystal sample of $5.67 \times 4.57 \times 3.19 \text{ mm}^3$ size give a pronounced indication of the ferroelastic phase transition in PbBiOBO_3 . In Fig. 8a a plot of the relative sample length change $\Delta L_i/L^0$ (with L^0 being the respective sample length at 413 K, $i = 1, 2, 3$) along each of the three orthorhombic crystallographic directions $[100]^{or} \parallel \vec{e}_1$, $[010]^{or} \parallel \vec{e}_2$ and $[001]^{or} \parallel \vec{e}_3$ is given. For temperatures within the range $343 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 413 \text{ K}$, i.e., temperatures above the phase transition, only linear changes of relative sample length with temperature are observed for each of the three crystallographic directions (see Fig. 8a). Consequently, thermal expansion of the orthorhombic high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 is constant with temperature, however, it possesses marked anisotropy with a sample elongation with rising

temperature (positive thermal expansion) along \vec{e}_1 and \vec{e}_2 and sample contraction (negative thermal expansion) along \vec{e}_3 , as it is given in Fig. 8a. From the slope of each of the relative length change curves in the range $343 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 413 \text{ K}$ the three coefficients α_{ii} of the tensor of thermal expansion of the orthorhombic high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 were calculated via $\alpha_{ii} = \frac{1}{L_i^0} \frac{dL_i}{dT}$, giving the tensor

$$[\alpha_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} 14.1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 17.3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -3.8 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}. \text{ The anisotropy of thermal expansion of the high-temperature phase of } \text{PbBiOBO}_3 \text{ is illustrated with a representation surface, where the absolute value of the "longitudinal" effect } \alpha'_{11} \text{ is plotted along a unit vector } \vec{e}'_1 = u_{1j}\vec{e}_j \text{ (} u_{11} = \sin\rho \cos\psi, u_{12} = \sin\rho \sin\psi, u_{13} = \cos\rho, \text{ with } \rho, \psi = \text{ spherical coordinates as defined in Fig. 8c) for all directions in space. Values for } \alpha'_{11} \text{ are calculated via } \alpha'_{11} = u_{1i}u_{1j}\alpha_{ij} \text{ from the tensor components } \alpha_{ij}. \text{ In the representation surface of the tensor of thermal expansion of the high-temperature phase of } \text{PbBiOBO}_3, \text{ given in Fig. 8b, positive thermal expansion is plotted in orange, negative expansion in dark green colour.}$$

Figure 8: Thermal expansion of PbBiOBO_3 . (a) Plot of temperature-dependent changes of relative sample length $\Delta L/L^0$ for the three crystallographic directions $[100]^{or}$, $[010]^{or}$ and $[001]^{or}$ (related to the crystallographic reference system of the orthorhombic phase), with $L^0 =$ respective sample length at $T_0 = 413 \text{ K}$. The initial heating curves, which differ from the measurements of the subsequent heating/cooling cycles due to a re-arrangement of the domain structure of the crystal (see text), are marked by the arrows of the left. The respective temperature ranges of the high- and the low-temperature phase are colour-shaded. (b) Representation surface $\alpha'_{11} = u_{1i}u_{1j}\alpha_{ij}$ of the thermal expansion tensor $[\alpha_{ij}]$ of the high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 (see also section 3.3). Positive values of thermal expansion are plotted in orange, negative values in dark green colour. The cartesian reference system $\{\vec{e}_i\}$, as defined in chapter 3.2, is indicated. (c) Sketch of the relation between the unit vector $\vec{e}'_1 = u_{1j}\vec{e}_j$ (with $u_{11} = \sin\rho \cos\psi$, $u_{12} = \sin\rho \sin\psi$, $u_{13} = \cos\rho$) and the cartesian reference system $\{\vec{e}_i\}$, ρ and ψ are spherical coordinates.

As seen by polarisation microscopy (chapter 3.1) twinning of the crystals of PbBiOBO_3 emerges at the ferroelastic phase transition on cooling, with domain walls of the twin domains being perpendicular to (001). Consequently, measurements of thermal expansion in the temperature range below the phase transition are performed with a polydomain sample and an evaluation of the tensor components α_{ij} is not possible because of the unknown mixing of α_{11} , α_{22} and α_{12} as well as the unknown influence of the domain walls. The $\Delta L/L^0$ data measured in the temperature range below the phase transition show, however, intriguing features: on one hand the ferroelastic phase transition becomes clearly apparent by a sharp bend of the $\Delta L(T)/L^0$ curves for the directions $[100]$ and $[010]$ (i.e., perpendicular to the domain walls), which indicates the occurrence of spontaneous strain of the crystals due to their ferroelastic behaviour (an analysis of spontaneous strain will be given below). On the other hand, the data show a difference between the initial heating runs and the subsequent heating/cooling cycles, which is very pronounced for the directions $[100]$ and $[010]$ and only weak for direction $[001]$. Correlating this behaviour with the observation described in chapter 3.1 of a change of domain

structure between the pristine crystal and the sample after its first heating to the high-temperature modification, the difference between the initial and the subsequent $\Delta L(T)/L^0$ curves could be traced back to a rearrangement of the domain structure of the crystal sample. This is further corroborated by the observed recovery of the initial domain structure of the polarisation microscopy sample after approximately one day and the corresponding observation of initial heating curves in thermal expansion measurements for each of the three measured crystallographic directions. Here the sample had been stored for 2-3 days between the different measurement sequences.

3.4 Temperature-dependent X-ray powder diffraction

To cope with the problem of a polydomain crystal described in the previous chapter 3.3 temperature-dependent X-ray powder diffraction data were collected within the temperature range $210 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 400 \text{ K}$. From the diffraction data lattice constants were calculated and refined by Rietveld refinement with the TOPAS software [18]. For diffraction data collected in the temperature range $210 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 305 \text{ K}$, resp. $325 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 400 \text{ K}$, structure data of the monoclinic phase, resp. the orthorhombic phase of PbBiOBO_3 that were derived from single-crystal structure determination (see above) were used as respective structure model, together with diamond structure data [19]. The diffraction data collected at 310 K, 315 K and 320 K were refined with both structure models for PbBiOBO_3 . The lattice constants of the monoclinic phase a^m , b^m , c^m , γ were transformed according to the transformation given in chapter 3.2 to monoclinic lattice constants A^m , B^m , C^m , Γ of the "orthorhombic-like" unit cell of the monoclinic crystal structure. The temperature-dependent lattice constants A^m , B^m , C^m are plotted in Fig. 9a together with those of the orthorhombic phase, in Fig. 9b the temperature-dependent evolution of the monoclinic angle Γ , given as $(90^\circ - \Gamma)$, is shown.

As can be seen in Fig. 9a the lattice constants in the temperature range 325 K – 400 K increase linearly with temperature, giving temperature-independent thermal expansion coefficients for the orthorhombic phase in accordance with the results from dilatometric measurements (see chapter 3.3). Linear fits of the data in this temperature range give $\alpha_{11} = 14.4(3) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\alpha_{22} = 18.7(4) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_{33} = -3.6(2) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which correspond well with the values derived from dilatometric measurements. Fig. 9a also shows that the temperature dependence of the lattice constants A^m , B^m and C^m of the monoclinic phase deviate slightly from linearity, but for all three cases polynomials of second rank match the temperature dependence well. Consequently, thermal expansion of the monoclinic phase of PbBiOBO_3 is not constant but changes linearly with temperature. Coefficients of thermal expansion of the low-temperature phase in the temperature range 210 K to 290 K were calculated from the temperature dependent lattice constant data via

$$\alpha_{11} = \frac{1}{A_0^m \sin \Gamma_0} \frac{d[A^m(T) \cdot \sin \Gamma(T)]}{dT}$$

$$\alpha_{22} = \frac{1}{B_0^m} \frac{dB^m(T)}{dT}$$

$$\alpha_{33} = \frac{1}{C_0^m} \frac{dC^m(T)}{dT}$$

$$\alpha_{12} = \frac{1}{A_0^m \sin 2\Gamma_0} \frac{dA^m(T)}{dT} - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{A_0^m \sin 2\Gamma_0} \cdot \frac{d[A^m(T) \sin(\Gamma(T))]}{dT} \right] + \frac{\cot \Gamma_0}{B_0^m} \frac{dB^m(T)}{dT}$$

with $A_0^m = 10.7853 \text{ \AA}$, $B_0^m = 10.5072 \text{ \AA}$, $C_0^m = 7.5290 \text{ \AA}$, $\Gamma_0 = 89.029^\circ$, all at $T_0 = 290 \text{ K}$. The coefficients α_{ij} are shown in Fig. 10a. Their temperature dependences follow linear functions of the type $\alpha_{ij}(T) = P_1 + P_2T$, the coefficients of the fitting polynomials (fitting between 210 K and 290 K) are listed in Table 2.

Figure 9: (a) Lattice constants a^{or} , b^{or} and c^{or} of the orthorhombic high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 , together with the transformed (see chapter 3.2) lattice constants A^m , B^m and C^m of the monoclinic low-temperature phase. The dashed lines mark the linear fits to the high-temperature lattice constant data and are extrapolated to the low-temperature region to allow the calculation of spontaneous strain (see below). The shaded area highlights the range of the phase transition, where Rietveld refinement of the X-ray powder diffraction data was possible with both, the orthorhombic and the monoclinic structure model. (b) Temperature dependence of the monoclinic angle. Here, using the transformed angle Γ its difference to orthogonality of the crystallographic axes, i.e., $(90^\circ - \Gamma)$, is depicted. The solid line is a guide to the eye.

As an example, at the temperature of 220 K the tensor of thermal expansion amounts

$$[\alpha_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} 21.9 & -183.9 & 0 \\ -183.9 & 44.0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2.5 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^{-6} [\text{K}^{-1}].$$

A transformation to principal axes $\{\vec{e}_i^0\}$ of the tensor gives

$$\text{the principal tensor coefficients } [\alpha_{ii}^0] = \begin{bmatrix} -152.3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 218.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2.5 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^{-6} [\text{K}^{-1}]$$

with an angle between the axes \vec{e}_1 and \vec{e}_1^0 (or \vec{e}_2 and \vec{e}_2^0) of $\varphi = 41.57^\circ$. To illustrate the anisotropy of thermal expansion of the low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 a representation surface of the tensor similar to the one given in Fig. 8b, is given in Fig. 10b, where, as above, the absolute value of the “longitudinal” effect α'_{11} is plotted along a unit vector $\vec{e}'_1 = u_{1j}\vec{e}_j$ ($u_{11} = \sin\rho \cos\psi$, $u_{12} = \sin\rho \sin\psi$, $u_{13} = \cos\rho$, with ρ , ψ = spherical coordinates) for all directions in space. Values for α'_{11} are calculated via $\alpha'_{11} = u_{1i}u_{1j}\alpha_{ij}$ from the tensor components α_{ij} . In the representation surface of the tensor of thermal expansion of the low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 in Fig. 10b positive thermal expansion is plotted in orange, negative expansion in dark green colour and the deviation angle φ between the axes \vec{e}_1 and \vec{e}_1^0 (equally for \vec{e}_2 and \vec{e}_2^0) is indicated.

Figure 10: (a) Coefficients of the tensor of thermal expansion $[\alpha_{ij}]$ of the monoclinic low-temperature modification of PbBiOBO_3 , calculated from the temperature dependent X-ray powder diffraction data for the temperature range 210 K to 290 K. Dots mark calculated values at the measurement temperatures, lines

represent linear fits of the data. (b) Representation surface $\alpha'_{11} = u_{1i}u_{1j}\alpha_{ij}$ of the thermal expansion tensor $[\alpha_{ij}]$ of the low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 for the exemplary temperature of 220 K. Positive values of thermal expansion are plotted in orange, negative values in green colour. The cartesian reference system $\{\vec{e}_i\}$, as defined in chapter 3.2, and the principal axes of the tensor $[\alpha_{ij}]$, $\{\vec{e}_i^0\}$, are indicated. φ denominates the deviation angle between the axes \vec{e}_1 and \vec{e}_1^0 (and equally \vec{e}_2 and \vec{e}_2^0).

Table 2: Coefficients of linear fits $\alpha_{ij}(T) = P_1 + P_2 \cdot T$ of the temperature dependent thermal expansion data of the monoclinic low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 , fitting range 210 K – 290 K. ξ is the sum of the squares of the residuals.

	P_1	P_2	ξ
α_{11}	$22.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-3.6 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-19}$
α_{22}	$45.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-15.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$8.6 \cdot 10^{-35}$
α_{33}	$-0.43 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-20.8 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-35}$
α_{12}	$-183.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-46.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$4.7 \cdot 10^{-16}$

As the change of the temperature dependence of lattice parameters between the orthorhombic and the monoclinic modification of PbBiOBO_3 implies, the ferroelastic phase transition is accompanied by spontaneous strain of the crystal that is additional to the normal response of a crystal to change of temperature. Spontaneous strain, a macroscopic physical property described by a tensor of second rank, depends on the point group symmetry change at the phase transition. Considering the symmetry change $mmm \rightarrow 2/m$ of PbBiOBO_3 , the spontaneous strain tensor $[\varepsilon_{ij}]$ is characterised by four tensor components, ε_{11} , ε_{22} , ε_{33} , ε_{12} . The coefficients ε_{ij} can be calculated from the transformed monoclinic lattice constants A^m , B^m , C^m , Γ and extrapolations of the (linear) temperature dependences of the orthorhombic lattice constants to the temperature range of the monoclinic phase, indicated in Fig. 9a by the dashed lines. For each applied temperature point the extrapolations give lattice constants $a_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}$, $b_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}$ and $c_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}$ that the high-temperature modification would possess had the phase transition not taken place. Spontaneous strain coefficients then result from

$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{A^m \cdot \sin \Gamma}{a_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}} - 1$, $\varepsilon_{22} = \frac{B^m}{b_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}} - 1$, $\varepsilon_{33} = \frac{C^m}{c_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}} - 1$ and $\varepsilon_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{A^m \cdot \cos \Gamma}{a_{\text{ext}}^{\text{or}}} \right)$, they are given in Fig. 11a for the investigated temperature range. The spontaneous strain due to the ferroelastic phase transition in PbBiOBO_3 can be separated into a "non-symmetry-breaking" strain, i.e. strain tensor components that are allowed for the point groups of both, the high- and the low-temperature modification of the crystal [20], here ε_{11} , ε_{22} and ε_{33} , and a "symmetry-breaking" strain, here ε_{12} , which is a shear strain component. The square of the symmetry-breaking strain ε_{12} is linear over the entire investigated temperature range of the low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 (Fig. 11b) suggesting second-order character of the phase transition [20]. A significant indicator for the second-order character also is the pure change in c_p during the phase transition without any trace of phase transition enthalpy ΔH , see Fig. 7.

The extrapolation of ε_{12}^2 to zero strain gives $T_c = 315.3$ K, which fits well with the DSC data while it is somewhat lower than the value derived from temperature-dependent polarisation microscopy and dilatometric measurements, probably due to a not ideal heat transfer between the single crystal sample and the temperature measuring point in both, the microscopy heating stage and in the thermomechanical analyser.

Figure 11: (a) Components of spontaneous strain of the ferroelastic low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 calculated from the lattice constant data given in Fig. 9 and the extrapolation of orthorhombic lattice constants into the temperature range of the monoclinic low-temperature phase, as described in the text. ε_{11} , ε_{22} and ε_{33} are non-symmetry-breaking strains while ε_{12} is a symmetry-breaking shear strain. (b) The linear temperature dependence of the square of the symmetry-breaking strain, ε_{12}^2 , is consistent with a second-order character of the ferroelastic orthorhombic \rightarrow monoclinic phase transition.

The phase transition in PbBiOBO_3 is accompanied by a small volume strain that results from the non-symmetry-breaking strain components, $V_s = \varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}$. Since ε_{11} and ε_{33} both are close to zero the volume strain arises mainly from ε_{22} and varies linearly with temperature.

A visualisation of the spontaneous strain in Fig. 12 with a representation surface analogous to those used above (section 3.3 and 3.4) for the thermal expansion tensors shows, that the directions of the extremal values of the deformation caused by the spontaneous strain coincide with the diagonal directions within the (A^m, B^m) -plane of the unit cell of the crystal structure. In Fig. 12 values of ε_{ij} at 290 K (i.e., at the temperature where the crystal structure of the monoclinic phase of PbBiOBO_3 was determined) are selected for the calculation of the representation surface. Here, the extremal values of spontaneous strain along the principal axes of the tensor are $\varepsilon_{11}^0 = 78.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $\varepsilon_{22}^0 = -91.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $\varepsilon_{33}^0 = -0.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$, with a rotation angle $\varphi = \angle(\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_1^0)$ of 42.1° . (For the representation surface the absolute value of the “longitudinal” effect ε'_{11} is plotted along a unit vector $\vec{e}'_1 = u_{1j}\vec{e}_j$ with $u_{11} = \sin\rho \cos\psi$, $u_{12} = \sin\rho \sin\psi$, $u_{13} = \cos\rho$, where ρ and ψ are spherical coordinates as defined in Fig. 8c for all directions in space, and values for ε'_{11} are calculated via $\varepsilon'_{11} = u_{1i}u_{1j}\varepsilon_{ij}$ from the tensor components ε_{ij} . In the representation surface given in Fig. 12, positive spontaneous strain related to an elongation is plotted in orange, negative spontaneous strain, i.e., a contraction, in green colour). The almost purely diagonal deformation of the crystal structure within the (A^m, B^m) -plane, that sets in when temperature falls below the phase transition temperature T_c of ~ 315 K, leads to a mere shearing of the crystal structure and the observed monoclinic symmetry, with only subtle changes in bond lengths and bonding angles, as analysed in Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Materials.

Figure 12: View of the crystal structure of monoclinic PbBiOBO_3 along the c -axis (for the labelling of atoms see Fig. 5), together with a representation surface $\varepsilon'_{11} = u_{1i}u_{1j}\varepsilon_{ij}$ of the tensor of spontaneous deformation $[\varepsilon_{ij}]$, both for $T = 290$ K. Positive values of spontaneous strain are plotted in orange, negative values in green colour. The cartesian reference system $\{\vec{e}_i\}$, as defined in chapter 3.2, the principal axes of the tensor $[\varepsilon_{ij}]$, $\{\vec{e}_i^0\}$ and deviation angle between the axes \vec{e}_1 and \vec{e}_1^0 (and equally \vec{e}_2 and \vec{e}_2^0)

are indicated. The scale bar refers to the representation surface of $[\epsilon_{ij}]$.

3.5 Vibrational spectroscopy

The vibrational spectra (IR and Raman) of PbBiOBO_3 recorded at room temperature are presented in Fig. 13. The selected temperature-dependent Raman spectra obtained during cooling run are depicted in Fig. 14. The recorded maxima of vibrational bands are listed in Table 3, which includes the bands observed at 298 K (IR and Raman) and also the position of Raman bands observed at temperatures of 395 K and 95 K. The number of expected vibrational modes for both phases (see Table S3 in the Supplementary Materials) was calculated using the Bilbao Crystallographic Server [21].

Figure 13: FTIR (compiled from FAR and MID IR spectra) and Raman spectra of PbBiOBO_3 recorded at room temperature.

The crystals of the low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 belong to the space group $P2_1/a$ (No. 14) with 7 atoms ($Z = 4$) per asymmetric unit, which occupy four-fold Wyckoff positions $e(C_1)$. The symmetry analysis of the optical vibrational modes gave $21 A_g(\text{RA}) + 20 A_u(\text{IR}) + 21 B_g(\text{RA}) + 19 B_u(\text{IR})$ modes.

The crystals of the high-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 belong to the space group $Cmce$ (No. 64) with 6 atoms ($Z = 8$) per asymmetric unit. The atoms B1 and O2 occupy eight-fold Wyckoff positions $e(C_2)$, atoms Pb1 and O1 occupy eight-fold Wyckoff positions $f(C_3)$, atoms Bi1 occupy eight-fold Wyckoff positions $d(C_2)$ and atoms O3 occupy sixteen-fold Wyckoff positions $g(C_1)$. The symmetry analysis of the optical vibrational modes gave $10 A_g(\text{RA}) + 8 A_u + 11 B_{1g}(\text{RA}) + 12 B_{1u}(\text{IR}) + 9 B_{2g}(\text{RA}) + 10 B_{2u}(\text{IR}) + 12 B_{3g}(\text{RA}) + 9 B_{3u}(\text{IR})$ modes.

The assignment of borate vibrational manifestations is based on the vibrational behaviour of an ideal trigonal planar BO_3 anion (point group D_{3h}), which exhibits four fundamental modes, $\nu_1 (A_1')$ symmetric stretching $\nu_s \text{ BO}$ ($850\text{--}960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_2 (A_2'')$ out-of-plane bending $\gamma \text{ BO}_3$ ($650\text{--}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_3 (E')$ degenerated stretching $\nu_d \text{ BO}$ ($1100\text{--}1450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_4 (E')$ in-plane degenerated bending $\delta_d \text{ OBO}$ ($500\text{--}600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and on previous spectroscopic studies of related borates [22-25].

The assignment of the bands of stretching vibrations of Bi-O bonds in BiO_6 coordination polyhedra is based on a previously published correlation diagram [26] between Bi-O bond length and Raman stretching frequencies. The lengths of Bi-O bonds in the PbBiOBO_3 crystals range in the intervals $2.185\text{--}2.551 \text{ \AA}$ and $2.161\text{--}2.587 \text{ \AA}$. Therefore, the vibrational manifestations of the Bi-O coordination polyhedron are expected in the region of $450\text{--}150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. According to the literature [27-29], bands of Pb-O bond vibrations forming PbO_6 polyhedra could be expected in a similar region.

The assignment of recorded vibrational bands of PbBiOBO₃ is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Recorded IR and Raman maxima (cm⁻¹) of PbBiOBO₃ and their assignment.

FTIR (cm ⁻¹)	Raman (cm ⁻¹)			Assignment	FTIR (cm ⁻¹)	Raman (cm ⁻¹)			Assignment
	298 K	395 K	95 K			298 K	395 K	95 K	
77m	50 vs	50 s	51 vs	Lattice modes	525 m	547 s	546 s	549 s	δ OBO
	60 vs	59 vs	62 m		581 m			572 m	
			66 m		606 w	598 w	600 w	606 w	
	84 vs	84 vs	86 s			622 w	621 w	624 w	
			92 sh			641 w	639 w	646 w	
	125 m	124 m	131 m		714 m			γ BO ₃	
				745 sh	730 w	729 w	731 w		
175 s	152 s	151 s	153 s	ν BiO, ν PbO	750 w	750 vw	750 vw	752 vw	ν _s BO
	161 m	161 m	164 m		902 w	909 m	907 m	910 m	
	199 vs	195 s	203 vs					1146 sh	ν _{as} BO
273 m	286 mb	285 mb	277 w	1188 s	1168 mb	1169 mb	1159 mb		
			302 w				1182 mb		
435 m	339 sh	345 sh	353 w		1216 s	1216 m	1211 mb	1233 mb	2γ BO ₃
			441 w			1432 sh	1430 sh	1435 sh	
	360 w		458 w			1456 wb	1453 wb	1459 vw	
						1500 vw	1500 vw	1505 w	

Note. Abbreviations and symbols: vs - very strong; s - strong; m - medium; w - weak; b - broad; sh - shoulder; ν - stretching; δ - deformation or in-plane bending; γ - out-of-plane bending; ν_s - symmetric; ν_{as} - antisymmetric.

FTIR (cm ⁻¹)	Raman (cm ⁻¹)			Assignment	FTIR (cm ⁻¹)	Raman (cm ⁻¹)			Assignment
	298 K	395 K	95 K			298 K	395 K	95 K	
77 m	50 vs	50 s	51 vs	Lattice modes	525 m	547 s	546 s	549 s	δ OBO
	60 vs	59 vs	62 m		581 m			572 m	
			66 m		606 w	598 w	600 w	606 w	
	84 vs	84 s	86 s			622 w	621 w	624 w	
			92 sh			641 w	639 w	646 w	
	125 s	124 m	131 m		714 m			γ BO ₃	
				745 sh	730 w	729 w	731 w		
175 s	152 s	151 s	153 s	ν BiO, ν PbO	750 w	750 vw	750 vw	752 vw	ν _s BO
	161 m	161 m	164 m		902 w	909 m	907 m	910 m	
	199 vs	195 s	203 vs					1146 sh	ν _{as} BO
273 m	286 mb	285 mb	277 w	1188 s	1168 mb	1169 mb	1159 mb		
			302 w				1182 mb		
435 m	339 sh	345 sh	353 w		1216 s	1216 m	1211 mb	1233 mb	2γ BO ₃
			441 w			1432 sh	1430 sh	1435 sh	
	460 w		458 w			1456 wb	1453 wb	1459 vw	
						1500 vw	1500 vw	1505 w	

Figure 14: Selected examples representing temperature-dependent Raman spectra of PbBiOBO_3 , recorded on cooling.

Temperature-dependent Raman spectra are depicted in Fig. 14. In accordance with the conclusions of the optical vibrational mode calculations, the figure shows that lowering the temperature has only limited impact on the overall characteristics of the spectra and the total number of observed bands. However, certain changes in the intensities and positions of the recorded bands were observed, primarily in the regions below 300 cm^{-1} (Fig. 14, right panel) and above 1100 cm^{-1} (Fig. 14, left panel). The intensity of the very strong band at 60 cm^{-1} gradually decreases during the cooling of the sample, while the intensity of the band at 50 cm^{-1} increases. Two broad bands of originally doubly degenerate antisymmetric stretching modes of the BO_3 group, with maxima at 1168 and 1216 cm^{-1} , split into three bands, with the lower wavenumber bands increasing in intensity. In addition to the discussed changes in the band intensities of the lattice modes and the splitting of the borate bands, certain changes can also be observed in the positions of other bands, as shown in Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 and in Fig. S2 (Supplementary Materials). The figures illustrate that the impact of temperature decrease on temperature-sensitive bands can be categorised into three groups. In the first group (see Fig. S2, Supplementary Materials), cooling results in an almost gradual shift of the band maxima towards higher wavenumbers. In the second group (see Fig. 15), cooling results in significant changes in the positions of the bands. The band maxima shift to higher wavenumbers, and there is also a notable alteration in the shape of the temperature dependence curve near the phase transition temperature ($T_c = 315 \text{ K}$). The third group depicted in Fig. 16 consists of a few bands that respond to a decrease in temperature by shifting to lower wavenumbers.

The observed temperature behaviour of the bands in the second group, which correspond to the lattice modes (see Fig. 15), apparently indicates the ferroelastic phase transition temperature of PbBiOBO_3 determined by the combination of the investigations given above. In general, the existence of vibrational bands whose wavenumbers decrease significantly (“soft modes”) during the phase transition from the paraelastic to the ferroelastic phase [30] serves as an important indicator of the formation of “optical type” ferroelastic materials [31]. However, the temperature-dependent behaviour of PbBiOBO_3 bands in the third group (see Fig. 16) does not fully correspond to the expected manifestations of soft modes. The medium-intensity band of mixed stretching vibrations of Pb-O and Bi-O bonds (maximum at 286 cm^{-1} at 298 K) splits into a doublet when cooled below room temperature, and one of its branches slightly shifts to lower wavenumbers, see Fig. 16a. Another “mode softening” is observed for two bands of ν_{as} vibrations of B-O bonds (see Fig. 16b) appearing only in the low-temperature phase of PbBiOBO_3 . So, the discussed temperature behaviour of these bands does not correspond to the typical manifestations of soft modes, which mostly represent lattice modes and precisely indicate the temperature of the ferroelastic phase transition.

Figure 15. The temperature dependence (cooling run) of the positions of selected bands of the second group in Raman spectra of PbBiBO_3 . The red line indicates the T_c temperature of 315 K.

Figure 16. The temperature dependence (cooling run) of the positions of selected bands of the third group in Raman spectra of PbBiBO_3 . The red line indicates the T_c temperature of 315 K.

Conclusion

Our temperature-dependent study by means of heating stage polarisation microscopy, calorimetry, dilatometry, Raman spectroscopy, X-ray powder diffraction and single-crystal structure determination of PbBiBO_3 reveal the occurrence of a displacive second order ferroelastic phase transition of Aizu species $mmmF2/m$ at about 315 K. Atomic displacements due to the phase transition are very small and the phase transformation is accompanied by a small change in specific heat, only. In the

ferroelastic low-temperature phase crystals of PbBiOBO_3 become twinned by domains of two monoclinic orientation states and predominantly a symmetry-breaking spontaneous shear strain ε_{12} arises. The longitudinal (non-symmetry-breaking) strain components ε_{11} and ε_{33} remain close to zero, a small volume strain V_s is caused by ε_{22} . The space group symmetries of the high- and the low-temperature phase, $Cmce$ (Nr. 64) and $P11\frac{2_1}{a}$ (Nr. 14), respectively, are in accordance with the irreducible representation Γ_2^+ of space group Nr. 64 [17] and correspond to a continuous, proper ferroelastic phase transition. The existence of a structural phase transition is also clearly confirmed by Raman spectroscopy, however, any characteristic soft modes are not observed during the cooling of the samples.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

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